

Seasonal Snow Melting Process Investigation in Polar Environment Using a Dual-Receiver Radar Architecture

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Abstract—With the arrival of spring and the rise in temperatures, seasonal snow coverage starts its melting process and undergoes significant metamorphic changes. Daily monitoring can help to improve the knowledge about this process. Field investigations conducted over a 15-day period in the polar station of Sodankylä-Tähtelä, Finland, utilizing the SNOWAVE system, a dual-receiver multiband and portable radar system in direct contact with the snow surface, revealed substantial day-to-day variations during the spring period. Through meticulous analysis of radar traces, researchers can discern trends in snow depth, density, and liquid water content in response to temperature fluctuations throughout this extended period. The paper presents the outcomes of this field campaign, demonstrating the possibility of employing innovative technologies for a monitoring throughout the snow melting process.

Index Terms—snow monitoring, melting process, microwave, radar, propagation, field campaign, cryosphere, polar environment, liquid water content

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate change has raised growing concerns regarding the dynamics of seasonal snow patterns, carrying substantial implications for hydrology, meteorology, and the management of natural resources. The seasonal snow melting process, in particular, holds crucial importance, influencing river levels, water supply, and flood risks [1]. In order to model the snowpack throughout this process and to be able to estimate and predict useful information in several fields as mentioned, some important parameters have to be investigated. The standard method approved by UNESCO for snow observation is the manual analysis, a very accurate method for retrieving several parameters such as depth, temperature, density etc. etc. Although this method is largely used, it comes with some drawbacks: it destructs the snowpack under investigation, it is time-consuming, punctual and operator dependant. The implementation of new technologies, such as microwave instruments, can help solve such limitations. Indeed, the use of radars plays a great role in understanding the complex dynamics of seasonal snow melting by retrieving snow parameters such as the snow depth (D), the density (ρ_{snow}), the snow water equivalent (SWE) and the liquid water content (LWC). Unlike traditional field measurements, radars can penetrate the entire snowpack, providing detailed data without disturbing the surrounding environment. Indeed,

radars can be employed in both ground-based and remote-sensing platform, such as satellite [2][3]. Common radars, such as ground penetrating radars (GPRs), in practical cases rely on information provided by other instruments (e.g. ultrasonic instruments, laser gauges, water content reflectometers etc.) or on *a priori* assumptions on the wave speed into the medium, in order to solve the analytical problem of retrieving both the depth of the snowpack and its electrical properties, expressed in terms of dielectric constant ϵ' [4][5].

Complex approaches are also possible, for example based on synthetic aperture radar tomography [6]-[9], but they often come with some practical limitations when used in the field because of their complexity. Instead, a new architecture, described in the next section, provides an alternative for effective, and rapid, field works. In particular, a recent radar system with a multiband configuration, SNOWAVE, is able to investigate the features of a snowpack in either dry [11][12] or wet [13][14] condition. This is possible thanks to its dual-receiver configuration which allows to record two measures at a time. In the next sections, the radar architecture and the concept behind this new configuration are presented, and the analytical process to retrieve the principal parameters of a snowpack under melting condition is used to analyze radar traces coming from a intensive multi-day measurement campaign in polar environment during April 2023. Values of D , SWE and LWC are presented, compared with the temperature trend experienced during the campaign.

This article is organized as follow: section II discusses the setup of SNOWAVE system used in the measurement campaign and the analytical process for snowpack investigation; section III presents the experimental validation of the concept through a field campaign in polar environment; in section IV the results are presented and discussed.

II. SNOWAVE: CONCEPT AND SETUP

The radar system employed for this campaign is called SNOWAVE and it is shown in Fig. 1. More details are given in [10]-[14], but the most important aspects are summarized here for sake of completeness and easiness of reading. SNOWAVE is a dual-receiver radar architecture normally used at the surface of the medium under investigation. It is composed by a FieldFox Keysight Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) which

Fig. 1. SNOWAVE radar architecture.

generates a continuous signal and, through a coaxial cable, sends it to a radiator. The radiator (tx in the picture) emits the signal, which penetrates inside the medium and, once reached the bottom, is reflected back to the surface. There, two different receivers (rx₁ and rx₂ in the scheme) at different distances with respect to the transmitter, s_1 and s_2 respectively, collect two signals related to the two different propagation paths. The two signals returns to the VNA where they are collected in the form of S_{21} parameter. The received signal carries the information related to the time of flight of the signal T travelling into the medium underneath, as in (1).

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &= d_1/v \\ T_2 &= d_2/v \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In this set of equations, the velocity v is unknown and depends on the dielectric properties of the medium. In the case of study where the medium is the polar snowpack during spring season, due to the increasing presence of water, both the real (dielectric constant) and imaginary part of the relative dielectric permittivity exhibit significant values. Nevertheless, the imaginary part is still very small with respect to the real part, and the following approximation can still be used:

$$v = c/\sqrt{\epsilon'} \quad (2)$$

From the geometry of the system, applying the Pythagorean theorem, the vertical depth of the snowpack D can be computed as in (3) knowing the distances travelled by the two signals d_1 and d_2 and the distances between the antennas.

$$\begin{aligned} d_1^2 &= (2D)^2 + s_1^2 \\ d_2^2 &= (2D)^2 + s_2^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Combining (1) and (3), the two times of flight become independent from the actual paths expressed by d_1 and d_2 , whose information is stored in the other parameters: by combining (1) and (3), the two times of flight become independent of the actual paths represented by d_1 and d_2 . Information about these paths is stored in the other parameters.

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &= \frac{\sqrt{(2D)^2 + s_1^2}}{v} \\ T_2 &= \frac{\sqrt{(2D)^2 + s_2^2}}{v} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Then, including also (2) and deriving the two unknown, i.e. D and ϵ' , the equations linked to the SNOWAVE radar architecture can be found (5)(6).

$$D^2 = \frac{s_2^2 T_1^2 - s_1^2 T_2^2}{4(T_2^2 - T_1^2)} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon' = c^2 \cdot \frac{(T_1 - T_2)(T_1 + T_2)}{(s_1 - s_2)(s_1 + s_2)} \quad (6)$$

After the computation of these two important and descriptive values, mainly dependant on the geometry of the system, a more accurate analysis on the wet snow condition can start. By knowing the amount of power collected at the receiving end, it is possible to compute the attenuation of water α_w reversing this formula, which derives from the two radar equations for each receiver:

$$\frac{P_1}{P_2} = \frac{G_1^2 S_1 d_2^4}{G_2^2 S_2 d_1^4} \cdot e^{2(d_2 - d_1)\alpha_w} \quad (7)$$

where P_1 and P_2 are the integral power collected by the two receivers, G_1 and G_2 are the antenna gains along the directions of interest, and S_1 and S_2 the radar cross sections at the snowpack-ground interface. Once the value of α_w is known, the approximation in (8) allows to find the value of the imaginary part of the dielectric constant.

$$\alpha_w \sim \frac{\pi f \epsilon''}{c \sqrt{\epsilon'}} \quad (8)$$

Here, both the real and the imaginary part of the dielectric constant are computed. The computation of the LWC, expressed as a percentage, and of the dry density (in kg/m³) can be done thanks to (9) [15].

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon' &= 1 + A + B + C \cdot \frac{1}{1 + (f/f_0)^2} \\ \epsilon'' &= C \cdot \frac{f/f_0}{1 + (f/f_0)^2} \\ A &= 1.83 \cdot 10^{-3} \rho_{ds} \\ B &= 0.02 \cdot LWC^{1.015} \\ C &= 0.073 \cdot LWC^{1.31} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 2. Example of set of measurements in L band. Each measure was carried out several time in slightly different positions.

Fig. 3. Snow condition on 21/04/2023. The liquid water on the ground was about 8 cm.

For retrieving these results, the frequency becomes an important character. For this set of observations, L- and C- band truncated waveguides were used, with central frequencies of 1.5 GHz (as in Fig. 2) and 6.75 GHz, respectively.

III. POLAR CAMPAIGN

In April 2023, a 15-day campaign was conducted in the Lapland region, specifically at the station of Sodankylä-Tähtelä, Finland. Initially, the 70 cm snowpack was in a dry condition with no visible signs of water content, but with large values of density. Over the following days, rising temperatures led to increasing humidity within the snowpack. By the end of this period, the snowpack had lost about the 50% of its thickness. The initial surface film of liquid water evolved into vertical channels, percolating through the snowpack to the

Fig. 4. Temperature observation during the days of the campaign. In blue, the frequent observation from the Finnish Meteorological Institute at the Sodankylä-Tähtelä station (ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/download-observations). The red dots are the observation in the test site done before the manual analysis.

soil below, accumulating several centimeters of liquid water, as visible in Fig. 3. After a previous test to understand the feasibility of the measurement, the snowpack observations have been carried out once or twice a day for two weeks in three different sites. The results of the measurements, here presented, are done only from the 16th to the 24th of April in a bog site placed approximately at 67°22' N, 26°39' E. Investigations were conducted in the L-band (1 - 2 GHz) and C-band (5.5 - 8 GHz) to ensure successful measurements under both wet and dry conditions, while also considering scenarios where the optimal band is unclear, particularly in the middle range. After placing the instrument on the snowpack's surface, several repeated measurements were done each time in slightly different positions (in an area of roughly 1 m²), in order to average the possible propagation inaccuracies, like uneven type of terrain, local surface roughness, etc. etc., as visible from Fig. 2. After each set of measurements, a snow pit has been dug and an investigation of the temperature, depth and density has been done through a standard manual analysis. The temperature measurements were used to confirm the presence of the water, and its trend can be seen from Fig. 4, where both *in-situ* measurements and official records from the Finnish Meteorological Institute are compared. The percentage of water in liquid form was estimated with a capacitive sensor from SLF (Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL - Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research), returning a percentage of LWC, but only when visible inside the snowpack. The computation of the LWC depends on the dry density of the snowpack, coming from external data detected at the beginning of the campaign. Several samples are taken each time, for each layer, and then averaged together in order to reduce the errors.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the analysis of radar data collected during the above-described campaign are depicted in

Fig. 5. Results of the campaign: in the graph above, the depth of the snowpack in meter measured with the snow probe (blue area) is compared with the results of the analysis of the radar data (red line). In the picture below, the percentage of LWC observed with the SLF snow sensor, in blue, are compared with the radar investigation, in red.

Fig. 5, and they are compared with the ground truth data. At the beginning of the campaign (up to April 18), the snowpack depth closely matched the ground truth data, which had been measured using a snow probe. During this period, the percentage of liquid water content (LWC) remained low, falling within the category of the so-called pendular regime. In this regime, water molecules glue the menisci of the snow grains, and air fills the gaps between the grains. In general, water droplets formed a thin film on the snowpack's surface but did not create proper channels within it. The quantity of water is in agreement with the air temperature which trends up to that date. Positive temperatures during the days allowed the upper layers of the snowpack to melt. However, due to consistently low nighttime temperatures, near or even below 0°C , the snowpack stored its thermal condition, even thanks to its natural high heat capacity. When, instead, the temperatures increase again also during night (from 18th on), the amount of liquid water increases and the depth of the snowpack decreases. Around the 20th of April, LWC reaches its maximum. Water had percolated into the snowpack, creating vertical channels (funicular regime) and accumulating on the ground, in some cases several centimeters deep. At this point, the snow-water

interface reflected most of the radar's power, preventing it from penetrating to the ground. For this reason, the red curve (i.e., snow depth retrieved by SNOWAVE) indicates lower values compared to the blue ground truth data. Thus, the difference between the two lines is largely due to this thick layer of water on the ground. As the campaign progressed, the LWC in radar measurements decreased as water drained into the ground, letting the snowpack free of a great amount of water. At the end of the campaign, with a drop in temperature, the liquid water froze during the night and the liquid water returns to be present as a film on the surface at the warmest hour of the day.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel approach for the observation of Arctic snow coverage during the melting season has been proposed. The analysis of radar traces, obtained with a portable dual-receiver radar system has been compared with daily snowpit measurements done in the same site. The behaviour of the snow cover, in terms of depth and liquid water content well agree with the temperature curve in the same day. The presence of high liquid water percolated inside the snowpack and then stored on the ground created an issue in the radar investigation. Indeed, the snow-water interface created a reflection of the radar signal, blocking the penetration of it all the way to the ground. This results in a lower value of D , together with a lower dielectric constant ϵ' , since most of the water was stored on the ground, under the interface. Despite the significant amount of water on the ground and the high percentage of liquid water content inside the medium, the signal collected at the receiving end was strong enough to yield good results, even optimal regarding the depth measurement. Further investigations will help to understand how to check for this water without any clue from the manual analysis.

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